

IRRIGATED-RAINFED RICE AREA MAPPING WITH CLIMATIC PARAMETERS OVER BANGLADESH

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Abstract: Spatial information on irrigated area is very important for crops water requirements, agricultural planning, water management, and climate changes. Bangladesh is one of the most climate risk vulnerable countries and 80% of fresh water used for irrigation and accelerating the climate changes impacts. Among the irrigation crops, rice is the highest water-consuming crops and 70% of the total cultivatable area of the country used for rice production. Moreover, the traditional flooded irrigation rice production producing GHG's especially methane, which accelerated the climate changes. Alternate wetting and drying (AWD) irrigation systems is the less water use and methane emission reduction techniques for a better solution to the dilemma. However, it is challenging to map irrigated rice areas by images classification methods due to the spectral similarity between with and without irrigation. In this study, we developed an index for potential irrigated rice area map for three different seasons by using remote sensing-based evapotranspiration (MOD16A2) and precipitation (GSMaP) data from 2003-2017. In this index, the crop evapotranspiration is higher than the effective precipitation in a region considered as irrigated area. Along with this, the land use and land cover (MOD12CQ) data used for agricultural area extraction. Further, the result compared with the FAO and National statistical irrigated data. The result shows the great variation of irrigated rice area among the rice cultivating season and climatic variables. The dry season irrigated rice area shows a good relationship with the FAO and national statistics, but the wet seasons irrigated rice areas shows a great deviation from the dry season's areas. Results from this study suggest that our method is a promising tool for mapping irrigated rice areas. The advantages of this study are its very simple methods, shows the seasonal variation of irrigated area and long-term trends, these are very helpful for rice cultivation planning, irrigation management and climate change mitigation.

Keywords: Irrigated, Rainfed, Rice, Climatic Variable, Remote Sensing

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Bangladesh is an agricultural country with a very high cropping intensity and diverse crop cultivating country. Almost, 70% of the territory dominant by agriculture land (World Bank, 2014). Bangladesh is the 4th largest per head rice consuming (500gm per per person) and rice producing country in the world (FAO, 2015). The rice is the dominant crop of the country and it covers three-fourths of all cropland area and contributes 70% of calories consumed (Majumder et al. 2016). Rice is the staple food for more of the half of world population and rice production sector is the largest consumers of irrigational water (GRiSP, 2013). Due to the drastic population growth (98 billion) growth need 70% more food (FAOSTAT, 2015) in 2050. But the arable land area of the country is even decreasing over time due to increasing demand for residential and industrial use (Hasan et al., 2013). Bangladesh also suffers from periodic natural calamities such as drought, flooding, and cyclones. Due to its location in a delta, climate change and associated sea level

rise are expected to increase the risk for flooding and salinization of agricultural lands, especially near the southern coast (Hossain and Silva, 2013; MOA-FAO, 2012). The rice cultivated areas of Bangladesh is located low-land, flat and inundate areas and these areas are easily damaged by natural disaster likes floods, drought and storms. The rice cropping pattern of Bangladesh are mainly three types- Boro Rice in dry season, Amon and Aus rice in comparatively wet season. The Boro rice is the main rice production and it's under fully irrigated condition. Due to the climate change and natural disaster during rainy season especially flood.

The drastic growth of world population is accelerated the pressure on global food supply (Godfray et al., 2010; Tilman and Clark, 2015). With one of the largest populations in the world, mainly composed of rural inhabitants who depend on agriculture as their principal income source, the competition for land and water throughout Bangladesh is huge and expanding. Bangladesh agriculture is a striking symbol of the long-term land use changes that have taken place in recent decades in south Asia Fig-1. The irrigation practices development leads green revolution and increased food production drastically. The Irrigation developments and yield improvement have been sustained by the construction of surface water use and shallow and deep tube-well irrigation pump also increased from 0.2 million to 10 million from 1985 to 2012. Currently, agriculture consumes more than 84% of the withdrawal groundwater (FAO, 2010).

Fig-1(b): Rice cultivated area and yield from 1970-2015. Source: BARC, BBS 1980-2014

Irrigation expansion and technological development can meet the food scarcity (Tilman et al., 2011). but there are limits of cultivated lands can offset the increase in food shortage in many regions but there are adverse and far reaching impacts on bio-diversity (Foley et al., 2011). Irrigated agriculture, which currently shares ~40% of the global crop production, is an important contributor to augment world food production, especially in semi-arid and arid regions (Godfray et al., 2010; Ozdogan, 2011; Thenkabail et al., 2009).

As a result, accurate information on irrigation extent, irrigation requirement and impacts of irrigation on environment are very important. There are a number of attempts have been taken for irrigation data set and irrigated mapping over the globe. The studies are mostly divided in to two categories – on the basis of scale, global and regional or national level; on the basis of data set- statistical data, model and simulation based and the spatial information or remote sensing based. Remote sensing is the most efficient and depended tools for the irrigated area mapping. The long-term phenology analysis, soil moisture and temperature analysis and the various indices analysis based remote sensing studies are becoming popular for irrigated area mapping. The global map of irrigated areas version 5 (GIMA5) used census-based statistics and produced irrigation equipped area with resolution of 5 arc-minutes from 2000 to 2008 (Siebert et al., 2005). The MIRCA 2000 (Portmann et al., 2010) also produced same data set on 2000. The GIMA (Thenkabail et al., 2009) used 500m remote sensing data and unsupervised classifier is the higher resolution map for world irrigation area. The Global Rain-fed, Irrigated, and Paddy Croplands (GRIPC) map (Salmon et al., 2015) has the highest spatial resolution (500 m) among these four products. These global studies are global scale and not effective for the local scale studies. These global data set does not represent the accurate irrigation data because the cropping pattern and irrigated area changing over the time. There are also a number of studies on local level, MODIS 500 m Spectral Matching Method in India (Dheeravath, v.,

Thenkabail, P.S., et al., 2010)), crop types and irrigation water use (Heller E., Rhemtulla, J. M., 2012) Zhu, X., Zhu, W., and et al. (2014) we developed three irrigation potential indices by using the time series normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and precipitation data. LI Bo-Lun, TI Chao-Pu, YAN Xiao-Yuan, (2017), multitempral cloud free data. Ferrant, S., Selles, A., et al. (2017), Detection of Irrigated Crops from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 Data to Estimate Seasonal Groundwater Use in South India. Most of the study are- phenology based, spectral matching, and spatial distribution. Moreover, there is very less significant irrigated area studies with remote sensing in Bangladesh.

1.2 Objectives

Irrigated area mapping for substantial year-to-year and seasonal variability in weather conditions complicates planning for water managers and agricultural producers and makes it difficult to apply standard rule-of-thumb approaches to agricultural water management. Hence, this study is an attempt to irrigated area mapping with long-term remote sensing data over Bangladesh. The main objectives of this study to map irrigated area over Bangladesh, along with asses the Alternative Wetting and Drying Irrigation technique. The objectives of the studies are-

- (i) Assessment of irrigated area with climatic parameter,
- (ii) Analysis the long-term and Seasonal variation of irrigated area,
- (iii) Comparison with relevant source of information.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Area

Bangladesh is being select as the study area. Bangladesh is a small country with 1,47,570 sqkm areas with 170 million people. The physically of Bangladesh is mostly low land alluvial deposited country with the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Meghna rivers is the largest deltas in the world (Ahmad et al. 2001). The country located at the lowermost reaches of G-B-M rivers system which drain 1.72 sq.km of land. Along with 230 rivers flow through the country like a complex network. The rivers are played very important rules in the culture, agriculture, transportation and livelihood of the countryman. But most recently due to the climate change and human intervention, the upper flow of the river decreased and most of the small river are dried up and the large river are also dried up and creates a lot of sandbars. As a result, the surface water flow and water reservoir of country decreased a lot. Conversely, groundwater irrigation has increased dramatically over the last three decades. The availability of surface water is not consistent because of seasonal variation. Ninety-five percent of the surface water in the river system also originates outside the country (Ahmad et al. 2001). This introduces uncertainty in surface water availability. For example, the availability of surface water in 1990 ranged from 3710 Mm³ during the dry season to 111,250 Mm³ during the wet season (BBS, 2013). Bangladesh experiences a tropical monsoon climate with significant variations in rainfall and temperature. Average annual rainfall varies from 1,200 mm in the extreme west to over 4,000mm in the northeast (Chowdhury 2010). About 80% of all rainfall occurs during the monsoon from June to September (Figure 3). In the post-monsoon (October November) and winter period (December–February), only 20% of the annual rainfall is available. Therefore, there is a seasonal water shortage depending on the duration of the monsoon. The map of the study arena is shown in fig-2.

Fig-2: Study Area with Global and MODIS RGB tiles

2.2 Data and Methods

For this study, the MOD16A2 data at 500 m spatial resolution, 8-day temporal resolution an atmospheric corrected data obtained from the United States Geological Survey database. The h26v06, h25v05 and h226v07 tiles covered the study area data from 2001-2017 used for Potential Evapotranspiration analysis. The data originally recorded using sinusoidal projection in the hierarchical data format (HDF) were mosaicked, resized to the study area, and reprojected and resample into 1Km resolution on the geographical coordinate system using the Modis reprojection tool (MRT) algorithm. The monthly potential evapotranspiration (PET) extracted from the MOD16A2 8-day time composite data. The monthly GSMaP data on 10 km Spatial resolution data used for monthly precipitation analysis.

The effective precipitation calculation methodology applied for monthly effective precipitation calculation. In this approach, a percent of total rainfall varying from 50 to 80 percent is assumed effective. That is, $R_e = P \times a$ (5) where, P is the growing season rainfall ‘a’ is coefficient (0.5 – 0.8). The equation used in India consider as this study effective precipitation calculation as:

Effective Precipitation (mm) = (RAIN - 5) x 0.75..... (Eq. 1)

The 10 KM GSMaP data resample in 1 KM resolution and produce a monthly effective rainfall data set. The FAO crop calendar for Bangladesh used as a reference crop calendar, the annual crop calendar divided into three major rice growing season- Boro (December to March), Aus (April to July), and Amon (August to November). Then, the GSMaP and MOD_PET monthly data composite into seasonal based. Crop water requirement is the water required by the plants for its survival, growth, development and to produce economic parts. This requirement is applied either naturally by precipitation or artificially by irrigation. The daily consumptive use of rice varies from 6-10 mm and total water is ranges from 1100 to 1250 mm depending upon the agro-climatic situation, duration of variety and characteristics of the soils. The major water required in the crop land for evapotranspiration and it’s come from precipitation or irrigation. The simple logic for the Irrigated area consideration is that, if the

MOD_PET – GSMaP effective precipitation = positive value means the area is under irrigation..... (Eq.2)

The seasonal irrigated area map prepared for the three different rice growing season. The irrigated crop area asses through the season and prepared a long term irrigated and rainfed area. The 16 days composite MODIS MOD13A2 dataset from 2001 to 2017 has been used for rice area mapping. MOD13A2 NDVI data with Kalmen filters data and support vector machine classifier have been used for sessional rice area mapping. Rice paddy map produced by Bangladesh Agriculture Research Centre (BARC) and Google images has been used as based map for ROI selection. In figure-3 shows the spectral classes of different rice and ROI images of NDVI. The overall flowchart of the research methodology shown in fig-4

Fig-3: Spectra of various rice (Left), ROI classes of MOD13A2 NDVI for SVM Classification

Fig-4: Flow chart of the research methodology

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Seasonal Rice area mapping

The rice area mapping is important for the irrigated-rainfed rice area mapping. The main three season rice in Bangladesh-i) Boro rice: dry and almost rainless season from December to March ii) Aus: wet and rainy season from April to July and iii) Amon: mixed wet and dry season from August to November. The three different season rice area are mapped and calculated the area. The Amon rice area is dominant and decreasing from 5.07 million ha in 2003 to 3.80 million ha in 2015. The dry season and yielded Boro rice area increasing from 3.39 million ha in 2003 to 4.86 million ha in 2015 in the study area. The Aus rainy season Aus rice area decreasing significantly in the study area. In fig. 5(a) shows the area of different rice area in Bangladesh and fig. 5(b) shows the comparison with the statistical data.

Fig-5 (a), (b): Estimated rice area and statistical rice area from BBS(2003-2015)

3.2 Seasonal Irrigated area mapping

The irrigated area mapping over Bangladesh is the most challenging due to the heterogeneities cropping pattern, high cropping intensity and the fragmentation of farm size. The long-term irrigated area mapping is a better way to face the challenges. In Bangladesh, cropping pattern follows the weather pattern and the natural calamities. During the dry and rainless season from December to March is less hazardous and good for the Rice production. Although, rice is produced under the flooded condition but due to the less natural hazard risk, most of the rice produced in this season. During this season the monthly precipitation rate is very low, almost rainless and temperature is also getting high and the evapotranspiration rate is also very high. In this condition the crops production under the flooded condition fully depended on irrigation. As a result, the irrigated area over Bangladesh during this season almost fully irrigated. The irrigated map on December to march shows almost all over of the country is irrigated.

Fig-6: Irrigated, rainfed and supplementary irrigated area in Bangladesh

The irrigated map for April to July and August to November are also shown in fig-6. In April to July and August to November season irrigated area decreased, and the non-irrigated area increased a high rate. The Irrigated Boro rice area increasing with the increases of Boro Cultivated area and due to the very dry and least rainfall there is no option for supplementary irrigated or rainfed rice area in this season. The Irrigated Amon area decreases as well as the rainfed and supplementary irrigated area fluctuated due to the overall decreases of Amon cultivated area. The Aus area almost rainfed area. The Irrigated, Rainfed and Supplementary irrigated areas shown in fig-7.

Fig-7: The Rainfed, Supplementary irrigated and irrigated Boro, Amon and Aus rice area.

3.2 Estimation the metrological parameter and Comparison

The monthly evapotranspiration is fluctuated all over the year from 80 mm to 130 mm, but the annual monthly precipitation distribution varied from 8 mm to 600 mm (Fig-5). There are few months like December to January the monthly precipitation is almost none, but the evapotranspiration rate is much higher than the precipitation. There is a huge water deficit for the crop water requirement, and they need alternative source of water which is generally as a mean of irrigation. The applied method for irrigated area estimation in this study shows a very good agreement in dry (Boro) and wet (Aus) season irrigated area estimation. But the mixed Amon season irrigated area shows a great difference between estimated and statistical sources of irrigated area. In fig-8(a), Monthly ET and precipitation data in Bangladesh and fig-8(b) the comparison between the applied method estimated irrigated area and the statistical sources of irrigated area.

Fig-8(a): meteorological parameters; 8(b) Comparison of estimated and statistical irrigated area.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS AND FUTURE WORK

The irrigated area mapping over Bangladesh is challenging due to the heterogenic cropping pattern and fragmented farm size. The aimed of this study aimed to calculate the irrigated area with long-term and seasonal variation aspects. The preliminary result shows a very good agreement to the national statistical data in dry and wet season irrigated area estimation but very poor agreement in mixed amon season. For the further study, analysis the annual irrigated area mapping from 2001 to 2017 and the compared it with the similar studies and national statistics in Bangladesh.

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